

Selective anchoring groups for molecular electronic junctions with ITO electrodes

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Contents

Contents	2
Synthesis details	3
S1. Synthesis and characterisation of target compounds	3
S2. NMR spectra of reported compounds.....	11
Break-Junction details.....	25
Absorption spectroscopy of wires 6-carboxylate, 7-acrylate, and 8-squarate	27
Surface characterisation experiments (XPS, QCM, AFM)	28
Current-time spectroscopy details.....	33
Transport calculations.....	34
Theoretical methods.....	39
References	40

Synthesis details

S1. Synthesis and characterisation of target compounds

General details: NMR spectra were recorded in deuterated solvent solutions on a Varian VNMRS-600 spectrometer and referenced against solvent resonances (^1H , ^{13}C). ASAP data were recorded using a Xevo QTOF (Waters) high resolution, accurate mass tandem mass spectrometer equipped with Atmospheric Pressure Gas Chromatography (APGC) and Atmospheric Solids Analysis Probe (ASAP). Microanalyses were performed by the Elemental Microanalysis service, Durham University, UK. All chemicals were sourced from standard chemical suppliers, except 4-((4-(acetylthio)phenyl)ethynyl)benzoic acid (**6-carboxylate**)¹, 5-bromo-3,3-dimethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzothiophene,² (4-ethynylphenyl)(methyl)sulfane,³ -hydroxy-3-(4-iodophenyl)pent-3-en-2-one,⁴ 3-hydroxy-1-(4-iodophenyl)but-2-en-1-one,⁵ and S-(4-(pyridin-4-ylethynyl)phenyl) ethanethioate⁶ which were synthesised according to published methods.

methyl-4-((3,3-dimethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzothiophen-5-yl)ethynyl)benzoate (a).

$\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (300 mg, 0.26 mmol) and CuI (49 mg, 0.26 mmol) were added to a freeze-pump-thaw degassed solution containing 5-ethynyl-3,3-dimethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzothiophene (500 mg, 2.65 mmol), methyl 4-iodobenzoate (696 mg, 2.65 mmol), Et_3N (5 mL) and THF (20 mL). The solution was stirred for 16 h before the solvent was removed. Purification was achieved by column chromatography eluted by a solvent gradient from DCM:hexane (1:1) to neat DCM forming a white solid. **Yield:** 0.39 g (46%). **$^1\text{H-NMR}$** (CDCl_3 , 600 MHz) δ 8.00 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.17$ Hz, 2H, H_e), 7.56 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.13$ Hz, 2H, H_d), 7.30 (dd, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 7.9$, $^4J_{\text{HH}} = 1.6$ Hz, 1H, H_b), 7.20 (d, $^4J_{\text{HH}} = 1.6$ Hz, 1H, H_a), 7.16 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.0$ Hz, 1H, H_c), 3.92 (s, 3H, H_f), 3.20 (s, 2H, H_h), 1.39 (s, 6H, H_g) ppm. **$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}\text{-NMR}$** (CDCl_3 , 126 MHz) δ : 166.5, 148.3, 142.3, 131.3, 130.9, 129.4, 129.2, 128.1, 125.9, 122.3, 118.4, 92.8, 88.1, 52.1, 47.2, 27.3 ppm. **MS(ASAP):** m/z 323.097 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$. **Anal. Calc.** for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 74.50; H, 5.63%. **Found:** C, 74.11; H, 5.69%.

4-((3,3-dimethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzo[b]thiophen-5-yl)ethynyl)benzoic acid (1). To a solution containing **a** (500 mg, 1.55 mmol) in THF (30 mL), KOH (173 mg, 3.1 mmol) in H₂O (10 ml) was added. The solution was stirred at room temperature for 8 h before the solution was acidified with HCl followed by extraction with DCM, dried over MgSO₄ before removing the solvent. **Yield:** 0.38 g (81%). ¹H-NMR (DMSO-d₆, 600 MHz) δ 13.14 (s, 1H, H_f), 7.97 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.5 Hz, 2H, H_e), 7.65 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.5 Hz, 2H, H_d), 7.37-7.34 (m, 2H, H_a+H_b), 7.29 (d, ³J_{HH} = 7.8 Hz, 1H, H_c), 3.25 (s, 2H, H_h), 1.35 (s, 6H, H_g) ppm. ¹³C{¹H}-NMR (DMSO-d₆, 126 MHz) δ: 149.2, 142.6, 131.8, 131.3, 130.0, 127.3, 126.4, 122.9, 118.0, 93.0, 88.6, 47.3, 46.8, 27.2 ppm. **MS(ASAP):** *m/z* 309.091 [M+H]⁺. **Anal. Calc.** for C₁₉H₁₆O₂S·½H₂O: C, 71.90; H, 5.40 %. **Found:** C, 71.63; H, 5.13 %

3-(4-((3,3-dimethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzo[b]thiophen-5-yl)ethynyl)phenyl)-4-hydroxypent-3-en-2-one (2). Pd(PPh₃)₄ (381 mg, 0.33 mmol) and CuI (62 mg, 0.33 mmol) were added to a freeze-pump-thaw degassed solution containing (4-ethynylphenyl)(methyl)sulfane (500 mg, 3.37 mmol), 4-hydroxy-3-(4-iodophenyl)pent-3-en-2-one (1.01 g, 3.37 mmol), Et₃N (5 mL), and THF (20 mL). The solution was stirred for 16 h before the solvent was removed. Purification was achieved by column chromatography eluted by a solvent gradient from DCM:hexane (1:1) to neat DCM forming a white solid. **Yield:** 0.38 g (35%). ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, 600 MHz) δ 7.54 (d, ³J_{HH} = 7.9 Hz, 2H, H_d), 7.44 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.3 Hz, 2H, H_a), 7.21 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.3 Hz, 2H, H_b), 7.16 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.3 Hz, 2H, H_c), 2.50 (s, 3H, H_g), 1.89 (s, 6H, H_h) ppm. ¹³C{¹H}-NMR (CDCl₃, 126 MHz) δ: 190.7, 139.5, 136.8, 131.9, 131.8, 131.1, 125.8, 122.5, 119.2, 114.7, 89.8, 88.9, 24.1, 15.3 ppm. **MS(ASAP):** *m/z* 323.090 [M+H]⁺. **Anal. Calc.** for C₂₀H₁₈O₂S·¼H₂O: C, 73.48; H, 5.70%. **Found:** C, 73.36; H, 5.63%.

4-((3,3-dimethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzothiophen-5-yl)ethynyl)pyridine (b). Pd(PPh₃)₄ (300 mg, 0.26 mmol) and CuI (49 mg, 0.26 mmol) were added to a freeze-pump-thaw degassed solution containing 5-ethynyl-3,3-dimethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzothiophene (500 mg, 2.65 mmol), 4-iodopyridine (545 mg, 2.65 mmol), Et₃N (5 mL) and THF (20 mL). The solution was stirred for 16 h before the solvent was removed. Purification was achieved by column chromatography eluted by a solvent gradient with neat DCM to neat diethylether, producing a colourless oil. **Yield:** 0.60 g (86 %). **¹H-NMR** (CDCl₃, 600 MHz) δ 8.61 (br, 2H, H_e), 7.36 (br, 2H, H_d), 7.30 (dd, ³J_{HH} = 7.96 Hz, ⁴J_{HH} = 1.62 Hz, 1H, H_b), 7.19 (d, ⁴J_{HH} = 1.59 Hz, 1H, H_a), 7.16 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.0 Hz, 2H, H_c), 3.19 (s, 2H, H_g), 1.38 (s, 6H, H_f) ppm. **¹³C{¹H}-NMR** (CDCl₃, 126 MHz) δ: 149.6, 148.4, 142.9, 131.5, 131.1, 126.0, 125.5, 122.3, 117.8, 94.5, 86.2, 47.2, 27.3 ppm. **MS(ASAP):** *m/z* 266.088 [M+H]⁺.

1-(4-((3,3-dimethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzothiophen-5-yl)ethynyl)pyridin-1-ium-1-yl)-2,3,4-trioxocyclobutan-1-ide (3). A solution of squaric acid (400 mg, 3.44 mmol) in acetic anhydride (30 mL) was heated under reflux for 1 h before the solution was cooled to room temperature. **b** (911 mg, 3.44 mmol) was added to the solution and then heated under reflux for 4 h forming a red solution. The solution was cooled to room temperature and the solvent was removed under *vacuo* leaving a red oil. The residue was triturated with methanol and the precipitate was collected by filtration. **Yield:** 1.03 g (83%). **¹H-NMR** (DMSO-d₆, 600 MHz) δ 9.23 (d, ³J_{HH} = 7.18 Hz, 2H, H_e), 8.17 (d, ³J_{HH} = 7.22 Hz, 2H, H_d), 7.48-7.46 (m, 2H, H_a+H_b), 7.35 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.00 Hz, 1H, H_c), 3.25 (s, 2H, H_g), 1.33 (s, 6H, H_f) ppm. **¹³C{¹H}-NMR** (DMSO-d₆, 126 MHz) δ: 211.5, 188.3, 164.4, 149.6, 146.0, 138.3, 135.5, 132.5, 129.4, 127.3, 123.2, 116.0, 105.7, 87.4, 47.3, 46.9, 27.3 ppm. **MS(ASAP):** *m/z* 362.078 [M+H]⁺.¹

¹ Elemental analysis consistently gave values consistent with the parent pyridine suggesting the ylide is not thermally stable.

3-(4-((3,3-dimethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzo[b]thiophen-5-yl)ethynyl)phenyl)-4-hydroxypent-3-en-2-one (4). Pd(PPh₃)₄ (300 mg, 0.26 mmol) and CuI (49 mg, 0.26 mmol) were added to a freeze-pump-thaw degassed solution containing 5-ethynyl-3,3-dimethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzothiophene (500 mg, 2.65 mmol), 4-hydroxy-3-(4-iodophenyl)pent-3-en-2-one (800 mg, 2.65 mmol), Et₃N (5 mL), and THF (20 mL). The solution was stirred for 16 h before the solvent was removed. Purification was achieved by column chromatography eluted by a solvent gradient from DCM:hexane (1:1) to neat DCM. Crystals were grown by evaporation of a DCM/MeOH solution. **Yield:** 0.25 g (30%). **¹H-NMR** (CDCl₃, 600 MHz) δ 7.53 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.3 Hz, 2H, H_e), 7.29 (dd, ³J_{HH} = 7.94 Hz, ³J_{HH} = 1.63 Hz, 1H, H_b), 7.19 (d, ⁴J_{HH} = 1.6 Hz, 1H, H_a), 7.16-7.14 (m, 3H, H_c+H_d), 3.20 (s, 2H, H_h), 1.89 (s, 6H, H_f), 1.39 (s, 6H, H_g) ppm. **¹³C{¹H}-NMR** (CDCl₃, 126 MHz) δ: 190.7, 148.2, 141.7, 136.7, 131.8, 131.1, 130.8, 125.8, 122.7, 122.2, 118.8, 114.7, 90.4, 88.2, 47.2, 27.3, 24.1 ppm. **MS(ASAP):** *m/z* 363.124 [M+H]⁺.²

3-hydroxy-1-(4-((4-(methylthio)phenyl)ethynyl)phenyl)but-2-en-1-one (5). Pd(PPh₃)₄ (381 mg, 0.33 mmol) and CuI (62 mg, 0.33 mmol) were added to a freeze-pump-thaw degassed solution containing (4-ethynylphenyl)(methyl)sulfane (500 mg, 3.37 mmol), 3-hydroxy-1-(4-iodophenyl)but-2-en-1-one (967 mg, 3.37 mmol), Et₃N (5 mL), and THF (20 mL). The solution was stirred for 16 h before the solvent was removed. Purification was achieved by column chromatography eluted by a solvent gradient from DCM:hexane (1:1) to neat DCM providing a white solid. **Yield:** 0.75 g (72%). **¹H-NMR** (CDCl₃, 600 MHz) δ 7.85 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.5 Hz, 2H, H_d), 7.58 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.5 Hz, 2H, H_c), 7.45 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.3 Hz, 2H, H_a),

² Repeated attempts were made to obtain elemental data but satisfactory results could not be obtained.

7.22 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.3$ Hz, 2H, H_b), 6.18 (s, 1H, H_e), 2.50 (s, 3H, H_f), 2.21 (s, 3H, H_g) ppm. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR (CDCl₃, 126 MHz) δ : 194.1, 181.9, 140.0, 134.1, 131.9, 131.6, 127.3, 126.9, 125.7, 118.9, 96.8, 92.2, 88.9, 25.9, 15.2 ppm. **MS(ASAP)**: m/z 309.100 [M+H]⁺. **Anal. Calc.** for C₁₉H₁₆O₂S: C, 74.00; H, 5.23 % **Found**: C, 73.82; H, 5.16 %

tert-butyl 3-(4-bromophenyl)-2-cyanoacrylate (c): 4-bromobenzaldehyde (8.18 g, 44.2 mmol) and 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine (7.47 g, 8.92 mL, 53.0 mmol) were added to a solution of tert-butyl 2-cyanoacetate (6.23 g, 44.2 mmol) in ethanol (30 mL). The reaction mixture was heated at reflux for 6 h, then cooled to 0°C forming white crystals that were collected by filtration. **Yield**: 5.80 g (42 %). ^1H -NMR (CDCl₃, 600 MHz) δ_{H} 8.08 (s, 1H, H_c), 7.82 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.6$ Hz, 2H, H_a), 7.62 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.6$ Hz, 2H, H_b), 1.57 (s, 9H, H_d) ppm. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR (CDCl₃, 126 MHz) δ_{C} 160.9, 152.2, 132.5, 132.0, 130.3, 127.8, 115.4, 105.2, 84.0, 27.9 ppm. **MS(ASAP⁺)**: m/z 251.967 [M-C₄H₉]⁺. **Anal. Calc.** for C₁₄H₁₄BrNO₂: C, 54.56; H, 4.58; N, 4.55 %. **Found**: C, 54.47; H, 4.57; N, 4.50 %.

tert-butyl 2-cyano-3-(4-((trimethylsilyl)ethynyl)phenyl)acrylate (d): trimethylsilylacetylene (2.27 mL, 1.59 g, 16.28 mmol) was added to a solution containing PdCl₂(PPh₃)₂ (1.19 g, 1.60 mmol), CuI (304 mg, 1.60 mmol), **c** (5.0 g, 16.28 mmol), Et₃N (10 mL) and THF (100 mL) that had been degassed by three freeze-pump-thaw cycles. The solution was heated to reflux for 16 h before the solvent was removed, leaving a brown oil. Purification was achieved by column chromatography on silica eluted by neat DCM to give a pale-yellow solid that solidified upon standing. **Yield**: 4.81 g, (91 %). ^1H -NMR (CDCl₃, 600 MHz) δ_{H} 8.09 (s, 1H, H_c), 7.89 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.1$ Hz, 2H, H_a), 7.53 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.1$ Hz, 2H, H_b), 1.56 (s, 9H, H_d), 0.24 (s, 9H, H_e) ppm. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR (CDCl₃, 126 MHz) δ_{C} 161.0, 152.7,

132.5, 131.2, 130.6, 127.8, 115.5, 104.9, 103.9, 99.0, 83.8, 27.9, -0.23 ppm. **MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 270.091 [M-C₄H₉]⁺. **Anal. Calc.** for C₁₉H₂₃NO₂Si: C, 70.11; H, 7.12; N, 4.30 %. **Found:** C, 70.13; H, 7.14; N, 4.00 %.

tert-butyl 2-cyano-3-(4-ethynylphenyl)acrylate (e): potassium fluoride (1.39 g, 24.0 mmol) was added to the solution containing **d** (4.0 g, 12.3), methanol (25 mL) and THF (25 mL). The solution was stirred at room temperature for 6 h, the solvent was removed under *vacuo*. The residue was dissolved in DCM, filtered and solvent removed from the collected filtrate under *vacuo* leaving a brown solid. **Yield:** 2.80 g, (90 %). **¹H-NMR** (CDCl₃, 600 MHz): δ_{H} 8.11 (s, 1H, H_c), 7.91 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.0 Hz, 2H, H_a), 7.57 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.1 Hz, 2H, H_b), 3.27 (s, 1H, H_e), 1.57 (s, 9H, H_d) ppm. **¹³C{¹H}-NMR** (CDCl₃, 126 MHz): δ_{C} 161.1, 152.6, 132.7, 131.6, 130.6, 126.7, 115.4, 105.4, 84.0, 82.6, 80.9, 27.9 ppm. **MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 198.057 [M-C₄H₈]⁺.³

tert-butyl 3-(4-((4-(acetylthio)phenyl)ethynyl)phenyl)-2-cyanoacrylate (f): Pd(PPh₃)₄ (231 mg, 0.20 mmol) and CuI (38 mg, 0.20 mmol) were added to a freeze-pump-thaw degassed solution containing **e** (500 mg, 1.97 mmol), S-(4-iodophenyl) ethanethioate (554 mg, 2.00 mmol), Et₃N (5 mL) and THF (20 mL). The solution was stirred for 16 h before the solvent was removed, leaving a yellow oil. Purification was achieved by column chromatography eluted by a solvent gradient from DCM:hexane (1:1) to neat DCM giving a pale-yellow solid. **Yield:** 0.438 g, (55%). **¹H-NMR** (CDCl₃, 600 MHz) δ_{H} 8.41 (s, 1H, H_c),

³ Too unstable for elemental analysis

7.97 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.2$ Hz, 2H, H_a), 7.62 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.2$ Hz, 2H, H_b), 7.58 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.2$ Hz, 2H, H_f), 7.42 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.2$ Hz, 2H, H_e), 2.44 (s, 3H, H_g), 1.59 (s, 9H, H_d) ppm. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR (CDCl₃, 126 MHz) δ_{C} 193.1, 161.1, 152.7, 134.2, 132.3, 132.2, 131.3, 130.8, 128.9, 127.6, 123.6, 115.6, 105.0, 92.5, 90.1, 83.9, 30.3, 27.9 ppm. **MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 404.132 (13%) [M+H]⁺, 404.132 (13%) [M-C₂H₂O]⁺, 348.062 (100%) [M-C₄H₇]⁺. **Anal. Calc.** for C₂₄H₂₁NO₃S: C, 71.44; H, 5.25; N, 3.47 %. **Found:** C, 71.21; H, 5.19; N, 3.27 %.

3-(4-((4-(acetylthio)phenyl)ethynyl)phenyl)-2-cyanoacrylic acid (7-acrylate): trifluoroacetic acid (5 mL) was added to a solution of **f** (200 mg, 0.49 mmol) in DCM (30 mL) and stirred at room temperature for 16 h before the solvent was removed. Methanol was added to the residue, sonicated forming to form a precipitate that was collected by filtration to give a pale-yellow solid. **Yield:** 90 mg, (52 %). ^1H -NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 600 MHz) δ_{H} 8.34 (s, 1H, H_c), 8.07 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.0$ Hz, 2H, H_a), 7.75 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.0$, 2H, H_b), 7.65 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.1$ Hz, 2H, H_f), 7.48 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.0$ Hz, 2H, H_e), 2.44 (s, 3H, H_g) ppm. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 126 MHz) δ_{C} 193.2, 163.5, 153.5, 134.9, 132.6, 132.5, 132.1, 129.5, 126.6, 123.1, 116.4, 104.9, 92.4, 90.7, 30.7 ppm. **MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 348.065 [M+H]⁺. **Anal. Calc.** for C₂₀H₁₃NO₃S· $\frac{3}{4}$ H₂O: C, 66.56; H, 4.05; N, 3.88 %. **Found:** C, 66.35; H, 3.65; N, 3.83 %.

1-(4-((4-(acetylthio)phenyl)ethynyl)pyridin-1-ium-1-yl)-2,3,4-trioxocyclobutan-1-ide (8-squarate): a solution of squaric acid (400 mg, 3.44 mmol) in acetic anhydride (30 mL) was heated to reflux for 1 h before the solution was cooled to room temperature. S-(4-(pyridin-4-ylethynyl)phenyl) ethanethioate (872 mg, 3.44 mmol) was added to the solution, then heated to reflux for 4 h giving a red solution. The solution was cooled to room

temperature, the solvent removed under *vacuo* to give a red oil. The residue was triturated with methanol to give a red precipitate that was collected by filtration. **Yield:** 1.03 g (86%). **¹H-NMR** (CDCl₃, 600 MHz) δ_H 9.51 (d, ³J_{HH} = 6.8 Hz, 2H, H_a), 7.96 (d, ³J_{HH} = 7.3 Hz, 2H, H_b), 7.66 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.4 Hz, 2H, H_d), 7.51 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.2 Hz, 2H, H_c), 2.47 (s, 3H, H_e) ppm. **¹³C{¹H}-NMR** (CDCl₃, 126 MHz) δ_C 208.5, 192.2, 189.2, 138.6, 134.4, 133.8, 133.10, 132.5, 129.2, 120.6, 109.9, 105.9, 87.0, 30.4 ppm. **MS(ASAP⁺):** *m/z* 350.047 (36.75%) [M+H]⁺, 254.065 (100%) [M-C₄O₃]⁺. **Anal. Calc.** for C₁₉H₁₁NO₄S·¾H₂O: C, 62.58; H, 3.47; N, 4.02%. **Found:** C, 62.89; H, 3.47; N, 3.86%.

2,3,4-trioxo-1-(4-(phenylethynyl)pyridin-1-ium-1-yl)cyclobutan-1-ide (9): a solution of squaric acid (400 mg, 3.44 mmol) in acetic anhydride (30 mL) was heated to reflux for 1 h, cooled to room temperature before 4-(phenylethynyl)pyridine (615 mg, 3.44 mmol) was added to the solution, heated to reflux for 4 h to give a red solution. The solution was cooled to room temperature, the solvent removed under *vacuo* to give a red oil, which was triturated with methanol to give a precipitate that was collected by filtration. **Yield:** 0.85 g (90%). **¹H-NMR** (DMSO-d₆, 600 MHz) δ 9.28 (d, ³J_{HH} = 6.8 Hz, 2H, H_a), 8.25 (d, ³J_{HH} = 7.3 Hz, 2H, H_b), 7.74 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.1 Hz, 2H, H_c), 7.59-7.56 (m, 1H, H_e), 7.53-7.51 (m, 2H, H_d) ppm. **¹³C{¹H}-NMR** (DMSO-d₆, 126 MHz) δ: 211.6, 188.3, 164.3, 138.1, 135.7, 133.0, 131.7, 129.9, 129.6, 120.3, 103.9, 86.9 ppm. **MS(ASAP⁺):** *m/z* 276.065 [M+H]⁺. **Anal. Calc.** for C₁₇H₉NO₃·¼CH₄O: C, 73.14; H, 3.56; N, 4.94%. **Found:** C, 73.24; H, 3.24; N, 5.09%.

S2. NMR spectra of reported compounds

Figure S 1 ^1H NMR of a recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 2 ^{13}C NMR of a recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 5 ^1H NMR of 2 recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 6 ^{13}C NMR of 2 recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 7 ^1H NMR of *b* recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 8 ^{13}C NMR of *b* recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 9 ^1H NMR of 3 recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$

Figure S 10 ^{13}C NMR of 3 recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$

Figure S 11 ^1H NMR of 4 recorded in CDCl_3

Figure S 12 ^{13}C NMR of 4 recorded in CDCl_3

Figure S 13 ^1H NMR of 5 recorded in CDCl_3

Figure S 14 ^{13}C NMR of 5 recorded in CDCl_3

Figure S 15 ^1H NMR of *c* recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 16 ^{13}C NMR of *c* recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 17 ^1H NMR of *d* recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 18 ^{13}C NMR of *d* recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 19 ^1H NMR of *e* recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 20 ^{13}C NMR of *e* recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 21 ^1H NMR of **f** recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 22 ^{13}C NMR of **f** recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 23 ^1H NMR of 7-acrylate recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$.

Figure S 24 ^{13}C NMR of 7-acrylate recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$.

Figure S 25 ^1H NMR of 8-squarate recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 26 ^{13}C NMR of 8-squarate recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S 27 ^1H NMR of **9** recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$.

Figure S 28 ^{13}C NMR of **9** recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$.

STM Break-Junction details

Single-molecule break-junction experiments were carried out using a modified STM (Keysight Technologies 5500 SPM). The system is equipped with a custom-built, 4-channel current amplifier based on the design originally reported by Meszaros et al.⁷ The signal from the 4 independent channels is recorded through a NI-9215 USB c-DAQ, with a sampling speed of 10 kHz. Tip positioning in the three axes is controlled by the STM electronics.

Before each experiment, a gold on glass substrate (Arrandee GmbH) was rinsed with acetone and then gently flame-annealed using a butane torch while placed on top of a silicon wafer to avoid bending of the glass. The substrate was then mounted into a liquid STM cell, and a few drops of 1 mM molecular solution were added. An STM tip was cut from a spool of 99.99+% gold wire (Goodfellow, UK). All experiments were performed at a bias voltage of 100 or 200 mV.

The STM tip was repeatedly driven a few angstroms into the substrate and subsequently withdrawn several nanometres, all at constant bias voltage, retraction speed, and while maintaining a fixed x-y position. The current signal (as a raw voltage) was continuously recorded during approach and withdrawal of the tip.

Raw data was converted into conductance-distance traces using a Python script (v.2.7, Python Software Foundation, <https://www.python.org>). Only data corresponding to the withdrawal portion of the experiment was used for analysis, and the approach data is discarded. Several thousand traces were collected for each molecule and presented without selection in logarithmically binned conductance histograms.

Figure S 29 shows gold-molecule-gold conductance histograms for all eight tolane wires. Clear molecular peaks are presented in panels B and G, which together form group A of the main text. Panels D, F, and H show the results for group B of the main text, with a mixed success rate for ITO selectivity. Finally, panels A, C, and E show the results for the three thiol-functionalised wires that we selected for further analysis.

From Figure S 29 it is clear that different contacting groups give different propensities for junction formation in gold-molecule-gold break junctions. **6-carboxylate** and **1** only differ in one anchoring group, namely thiol versus DMBT. The DMBT surface binding group has been shown as a very effective anchor for gold break junctions (ref. 20 of main manuscript) and indeed here this is demonstrated by a strong histogram peak for **1** (Panel B of Figure S 29) compared to a very weak peak for **6-carboxylate** (Panel A). **7-acrylate** (Panel E) and **5** (Panel H) both give distinguishable histogram peaks but they are clearly not as effective at forming defined junctions as **1** (Panel B) or **2** (Panel G). Counterintuitively, **2** (Panel G) forms

more distinctive histograms than **4** (Panel F). These collected results show a complex pattern of junction formation propensities for these gold-molecule-gold junctions depending on molecular structure, which could arise from junction formation energetics or dynamics. On the other hand, **3** and **8-squarate** show no signs of junction formation in gold-molecule-gold break junctions. This gives the most important result of this screening which is that the two compounds with a squarate anchoring group give no junction formation propensity with gold electrodes.

Figure S 29 Single-molecule conductance histograms show the presence or absence of gold-molecule-gold junctions. Insets show molecular structures of each wire. Histograms in C, D, and F do not show a molecular feature. Junction formation probability varies between histograms that show a molecular feature; High formation probability in B and G, and lower formation probability in A, E, and H.

Absorption spectroscopy of wires 6-carboxylate, 7-acrylate, and 8-squarate

UV-VIS absorption measurements were carried out on a Jenway 7305 spectrophotometer in appropriate solvents, **6-carboxylate** and **7-acrylate** in the same solvent as their STM-BJ conductance measurements, see Figure S 30. These electronic spectra show that the main absorption bands shift with structure. Since the molecules have similar conductance values it suggests that contact chemistry is having a large influence on the observed conductances.

Figure S 30 Optical band-gap estimation from UV-VIS absorption spectra shows that 8-squarate has the smallest gap, followed by 7-acrylate and then 6-carboxylate. Absorption profiles for wires 6-carboxylate (blue), 7-acrylate (gray), and 8-squarate (red). The dotted lines show estimated shoulders for the HOMO-LUMO gaps of each wire.

Surface characterisation experiments (XPS, QCM, AFM)

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to gain insight into the binding interactions between these specific anchoring groups (carboxylic acid, cyanoacrylic acid and pyridinium squarate) and the different substrates used (ITO and gold). For this purpose adsorbed monolayers of these compounds were formed on both substrates from 10^{-4} M solutions in THF:chloroform (1:4), prior to transferring to the UHV XPS chamber for analysis. A Kratos AXIS Ultra DLD spectrometer equipped with a monochromatic Al $K\alpha$ X-ray source (1486.6 eV) with a pass energy of 20 eV and a photoelectron take-off angle of 90° with respect to the sample plane was used. The C1s peak at 284.6 eV was used for calibration of energies. The middle column of Figure S 31 shows the XPS data for the S2p region for the powder sample of **6-carboxylate**, **7-acrylate**, and **8-squarate**. All these powder samples display two peaks with an area ratio of $\sim 2:1$ which are assigned to ($2p_{3/2}$) and ($2p_{1/2}$), respectively, with the splitting arising from spin-orbit effects. The respective area ratios for the $2p_{3/2}$ and $2p_{1/2}$ peaks are 60.6% and 39.4% for **6-carboxylate**, 61.1% and 38.9% for **7-acrylate** and 61.8% and 38.2% for **8-squarate**. The peaks lie at 163.5 and 164.7 eV for **6-carboxylate**, 163.4 and 164.5 eV for **7-acrylate** and 163.3 and 164.5 eV for **8-squarate** (peak separation of ~ 1.2 eV).⁸⁻⁹

By contrast, the XPS data from SAM of **6-carboxylate**, **7-acrylate**, and **8-squarate** on a gold substrate are more convoluted (Figure S 31, left column). For **6-carboxylate**, the XPS data displays three peaks at 164.8, 163.6 and 162.2 eV (Figure S 31, top left). The peak at 164.8 eV and the corresponding stronger $2p_{3/2}$ peak at 163.6 eV (1.2 eV higher in energy) appear at practically the same binding energy as those observed for the powder sample (164.7 and 163.5 eV), revealing that **6-carboxylate** does interact with the gold substrate exclusively through the thiol end. The lower binding energy peak at 162.2 eV is assigned to the $2p_{3/2}$ peak of a sulfur atom in contact with the gold substrate. This $2p_{3/2}$ peak would pair with a weaker $2p_{1/2}$ peak, which would be expected to fall ca. 1.2 eV higher in energy (i.e. at 163.4 eV). The observed signal is, therefore, the convolution of contributions from surface-bonded and free sulfur atoms.¹⁰⁻¹² This leads us to conclude that in the case of SAMs of **6-carboxylate**, adsorbate molecules are adsorbed onto the gold substrate through either the thiol or the carboxylic group, without pronounced selectivity. The relative areas of the XPS peaks from sulfur not bonded and bonded to the gold substrate are 35:65 (Figure S31), implying that sulfur has a slight predominance to be bonded to gold in SAMs of **6-carboxylate**.

Figure S 31 XPS data recorded in the S2p region for 6-carboxylate, 7-acrylate, and 8-squarate as powder (middle) as a SAM on gold (left) and as SAM on ITO (right).

Similar XPS results are obtained for **7-acrylate**. The XPS data from SAM of **7-acrylate** on gold shows three peaks at 164.7, 163.4 and 161.9 eV (Figure S 31, middle left). The peak at 164.7 eV and the part of the corresponding stronger $2p_{3/2}$ peak at 163.5 eV are attributed to thiol moieties not bound to the gold substrate supporting the monolayer. On the other hand, the peak at 161.9 eV is assigned to the $2p_{3/2}$ peak of a thiol sulfur atom bound to the gold substrate, and this is paired with a corresponding weaker $2p_{1/2}$ peak expected to fall ca. 1.2 eV higher in energy (i.e. at 163.1 eV). Thus, the SAM of **7-acrylate** shows similar XPS behaviour to that of **6-carboxylate**, with the molecules either contacting the gold substrate through the thiol or the cyanoacrylic end. However, when comparing **7-acrylate** with **6-carboxylate**, the former shows higher ratios of free to surface-bonded sulfur with area ratios of 52:48 (Figure S 31, middle left).

Finally, XPS data for a SAM of **8-squarate** on gold shows two intense peaks at 163.2 and 161.8 eV (Figure S 31, bottom left) and a weak peak at 164.4 eV. The strong peak at 161.8 eV is assigned to the $2p_{3/2}$ feature of sulfur bonded as thiol to the gold surface. This would pair with a weaker $2p_{1/2}$ peak, that is expected to fall ca. 1.2 eV higher in energy, i.e. at 163.0 eV which aligns well with the peak observed at 163.2 eV. The very weak peak at 164.4 eV is

at the energy expected for the $2p_{1/2}$ resonance of sulfur not bonded to the gold surface. We conclude that molecules in a SAM of **8-squarate** interact with the gold substrate preferably via the thiol group, with very little surface binding through the pyridinium squarate group. The relative areas of XPS signals arising from thiols not bonded and bonded to the gold substrate, 16:84 (Figure S 31, bottom left) support this conclusion. This result was further confirmed using a quartz crystal microbalance (QCM). A QCM resonator was incubated in a 10^{-4} M solution of **9** (a tolane with only a pyridinium squarate terminus) in THF:chloroform (1:4) and the frequency was monitored with time. After 48 hours of incubation, no variation in the frequency with respect to the bare QCM resonator was observed, demonstrating no adsorption of pyridinium squarate-capped molecules onto the gold substrate.

However, when an ITO substrate was used to support the SA monolayers of **6-carboxylate**, **7-acrylate**, and **8-squarate**, the XPS data show only two peaks at 164.7 and 163.5 eV for **6-carboxylate** (Figure S 31, top right), at 164.5 and 163.3 eV for **7-acrylate** (Figure S 31, middle right) and at 164.6 and 163.5 eV for **8-squarate** (Figure S 31, bottom right). All these peaks appear at practically the same position to those observed for the respective powders indicating that when an ITO substrate is used to support the monolayer the interaction of the molecules of **6-carboxylate**, **7-acrylate**, and **8-squarate** is through the carboxylic acid, cyanoacrylic acid and pyridinium squarate, respectively, with the thiol group facing away from the surface and not in contact with the ITO. Therefore, these results demonstrate the specific affinity of the carboxylic acid, cyanoacrylic acid and pyridinium squarate towards an ITO substrate versus the thiol group.

Next, the N1s region was analysed at high resolution, to obtain more information about the interaction of the new pyridinium squarate adsorbate group with an ITO substrate. The XPS data for the powder shows an intense peak at 401.6 eV attributed to the positively charged nitrogen (N^+),¹³ and a less intense peak at 398.6 eV associated to the radical cation formed during X-ray excitation in the analysis chamber of the XPS instrument (**Figure S 32**, top panel).¹⁴ For a SAM of **8-squarate** on ITO two peaks appear at the same binding energies to these observed for the powder; indicating the absence of an interaction between the N atom of the pyridinium squarate group and the substrate (**Figure S 32**, bottom panel). Thus, the interaction of the pyridinium squarate group with the ITO has to occur through the O atoms. It is noteworthy to indicate here that the high-resolution O1s region was not analysed since an ITO substrate is expected to have multifarious oxygen species which would mask any potential peaks attributed to the pyridinium squarate.

Figure S 32 XPS data recorded in the N1s region for 8-squarate as powder and as SAM on ITO.

For the nanolithographic indentation of a molecular SAM on ITO, the substrate was mounted into a commercial AFM (Keysight Technologies 5500 SPM) equipped with a contact mode nose cone and a silicon cantilever. The laser was aligned onto the centre of the photodiode before approaching. Once in contact, a surface image was recorded in contact mode using a force setpoint of ~ 5 nN, followed by reducing the scan area to record a second smaller image in the centre of the first. This second image was recorded at a force of ~ 20 nN, after which the first scan was repeated at ~ 5 nN.

AFM contact mode images of an ITO substrate with an adsorbed layer of **6-carboxylate** present (top) are contrasted with a bare ITO substrate (bottom) in Figure S 33. In each case, the left panel shows a scan of the ITO substrate prior to applying a high contact force. The inset in the centre shows a magnified (zoomed-in) area where the large contact force was applied. The right panel shows the same scan area as the left panel after zooming back out after application of the high contact forces. The substrate that had a monolayer (top) clearly shows that it has been damaged or deformed by the high contact force, whereas the bare substrate (bottom) shows no signs of damage.

Figure S 33 AFM imaging in contact-mode confirms the presence of a self-assembled monolayer of 6-carboxylate on ITO by carving a small square using a high force. The ITO surface is imaged with a self-assembled monolayer of 6-carboxylate molecules (top) and without any molecules (bottom). The left two panels show scans of the ITO surfaces before carving using a relatively low force setpoint. The middle two smaller panels show areas zoomed-in onto the left panel at a high force setpoint. The right two panels are the same areas as on the left, after the nano-indentation. Only the surface with self-assembled molecules shows a carved patch in the monolayer after the experiment.

Current-time spectroscopy details

For experiments with indium tin oxide (ITO) electrodes, glass substrates were purchased from SPI Supplies (USA) with a 700 nm layer of ITO. The exception is the AFM nano-indentation experiment, for which glass substrates with a 40 nm layer of ITO were used (Präzisions Glas & Optik GmbH, PGO, Germany). The substrates from SPI Supplies were cut into squares of roughly 12x12 mm with a diamond pen. They were cleaned according to Chockalingam et al.¹⁵ where they were first sonicated in DCM for ~20 minutes, then in methanol for another ~20 minutes, and finally for ~30 min in a 0.5 M solution of potassium carbonate in a 3:1 mixture of methanol:Milli-Q water. The substrates were then immersed for ~48 hours in 1 mM solutions of target molecules in 1:1 DCM:ethanol. STM-I(t) experiments for **6-carboxylate** and **8-squarate** were carried out in air, whereas TMB was added to the measurement of **7-acrylate**.

A gold STM tip was freshly cut for each experiment and positioned a few angstroms from the substrate using a setpoint current of ~5 nA. The feedback loop was then switched off to allow for fluctuations and jumps in the current to be monitored. Once the current was relatively stable, i.e. the baseline remains mostly horizontal, segments of 0.5 seconds were saved as raw data. Approximately 400 traces were saved for **6-carboxylate** when stochastic current jumps were observed. Approximately 2000 traces for **7-acrylate** and **8-squarate** were saved regardless of whether any jumps were observed.

Raw I(t) traces were processed using two bespoke Python scripts (v.2.7, Python Software Foundation, <https://www.python.org>). The first script uses an automated routine to fit the background current to a sloped straight line that is then subtracted from the trace. After this process, the baseline current is zero, and the magnitude of the current jump can be established relative to the background. The processed traces were then used to compile the histograms shown in the main text, Figure 4A-C.

The processed traces were then subjected to a second algorithm, which aim is to “slice” the traces between abrupt changes in current (“jumps”) to obtain additional information on the temporal stability of the junction. The algorithm calculates the second derivative of the smoothed (7-point moving median filter) current trace, and cuts (dumps data to a new file) when its value is above a pre-defined threshold. The algorithm also automatically rejects traces shorter than 1 ms as attributed to noise unfiltered by the moving median smoothing. These “slices” of data were then used to compile the density maps presented in the main text, Figure 4D-F. Details on the two algorithms, with example data and relative plots, can be found in the supporting information of our previous publications on the subject.¹⁶⁻¹⁷

Transport calculations

Figure S 34 shows two different possible binding configurations of COO^- or COOH to an ITO.

Figure S 34 Possible binding structure of COO^- or COOH H-bonding groups to metal oxide surfaces. Adapted with permission from reference ¹⁸. Copyright 2014 John Wiley and Sons.

To find the most stable configuration, we have calculated the binding energy E_B of the structures shown in Figure S 34 for all three molecules as illustrated in Table S1. We found that COO^- has a stronger binding to ITO.

Table S1. Binding energy of COO^- or COOH groups to metal oxide surfaces.

Possible binding configuration	Configuration1	Configuration2
6-carboxylate	-3.2 eV	-0.54 eV
7-acrylate	-3.0 eV	-0.57 eV
8-squarate	-3.15 eV	-1.28 eV

Figure S 35 shows the relaxed structure of the junctions for **6-carboxylate**, **7-acrylate**, and **8-squarate** between gold and ITO electrodes using the COO^- binding structure. To study the effect of the binding configuration on electrical conductance, we have then compared the electrical conductance of **6-carboxylate** using the binding configuration 1 and 2 shown in Figure S 34. As shown in Figure S 36, the overall conductance of the configuration 2 is higher than that of 1. Based on the binding energy calculations, the junction formation probability of COOH is expected to be lower than that of COO^- , although both configurations are energetically possible at room temperature ($E_B > 25\text{meV}$). Therefore, we calculate the

transmission coefficient for three different energetically optimised binding configurations of each molecule as shown in figure S 37. We found that the overall trend for the average conductances over different configurations are in agreement with experiment for a wide range of Fermi energies around DFT Fermi energy. As shown in table S2, the best agreement between experiment and theory is found at $E_F = -0.78$ eV. We note that the calculations using ITO is computationally very demanding.

Figure S 35 Relaxed structure of the molecules connected to the gold and ITO.

Table S2. Comparison between conductance in the units of G_0 between experimentally measured values and those calculated by averaging conductances for different configurations of each molecule (Figure S 37D). Although the trend predicted from DFT is in a good agreement with experiment, the calculated conductance values are higher than measured values. This is expected because DFT is well-known to overestimate the conductance values.

Molecule	Conductance (G_0)	
	Calculation	Experiment
6-carboxylate	1.1×10^{-3}	9.2×10^{-5}
7-acrylate	2.3×10^{-4}	5.9×10^{-5}
8-squarate	4.1×10^{-4}	7.2×10^{-5}

Figure S 36 Relaxed structure of the molecules connected to ITO using two different binding configurations and corresponding electrical conductances.

Figure S 37 A-C) Electrical conductances of the molecules 6-carboxylate, 7-acrylate and 8-squarate connected to ITO using three different configurations. D) Average of electrical conductances for the molecules.

We have also calculated the electrical conductance of **6-carboxylate**, **7-acrylate**, and **8-squarate** between gold-gold electrodes (Figure SA) and we found that the electrical conductance of **6-carboxylate** is slightly higher than that of **7-acrylate** (Figure SB) in agreement with the measurement (Figure S 29). This is due to the HOMO level in **6-carboxylate** being closer to the Fermi energy compared to **7-acrylate**, which leads to higher conductance. We also found that the electrical conductance of **8-squarate** is lower than molecules **6** and **7**.

Figure S 38 A) Relaxed structure of the molecules between gold-gold electrodes. B) Electrical conductance of the molecules

Figure S 39. An example of 8-squarate binding configuration to ITO. Two oxygen atoms interact with ITO. The bond length between one oxygen atom in squarate and the H atom of ITO indicates that a hydrogen bond has formed. The other oxygen atom in squarate interacts electrostatically with the surface of ITO.

Theoretical methods

The optimised geometry, ground state Hamiltonian and overlap matrix element of each structure was self-consistently obtained using the SIESTA¹⁹ implementation of density functional theory (DFT). SIESTA employs norm-conserving pseudopotentials to account for the core electrons, and linear combinations of atomic orbitals to construct the valence states. The generalised gradient approximation (GGA) of the exchange and correlation functional is used with the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof parameterisation (PBE) a double- ζ polarised (DZP) basis set, a real-space grid defined with an equivalent energy cut-off of 250 Ry. The geometry optimisation for each structure is performed to achieve forces smaller than 10 meV / Å.

The mean-field Hamiltonian obtained from the converged DFT calculation was combined with Gollum²⁰ implementation of the non-equilibrium Green's function method²¹ to calculate the phase-coherent, elastic scattering properties of each system consisting of left gold (source) and right gold (drain) leads and the scattering region. The transmission coefficient $T(E)$ for electrons of energy E (passing from the source to the drain) is calculated via the relation: $T(E) = \text{Trace}(\Gamma_R(E)G^R(E)\Gamma_L(E)G^{R\dagger}(E))$. In this expression, $\Gamma_{L,R}(E) = i(\Sigma_{L,R}(E) - \Sigma_{L,R}^\dagger(E))$ describe the level broadening due to the coupling between left (L) and right (R) electrodes and the central scattering region, $\Sigma_{L,R}(E)$ are the retarded self-energies associated with this coupling and $G^R = (ES - H - \Sigma_L - \Sigma_R)^{-1}$ is the retarded Green's function, where H is the Hamiltonian and S is overlap matrix. Using obtained transmission coefficient $T(E)$, the conductance could be calculated by Landauer formula ($G = G_0 \int dE T(E)(-\partial f/\partial E)$) where $G_0 = 2e^2/h$ is conductance quantum.

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